

AVERAGE AREA, PRODUCTION AND YIELD OF COTTON IN MARATHWADA REGION.

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Abstract

Cotton (gossypium spp) the white gold is one of the most important cash crop in the world. although cotton is primary a fibre crop ,it is also used as a food and feed crop. Cotton seed being the world`s second most oilseeds used for culinary purposes and the oil cake residue is a protein rich feed for ruminant livestock. Cotton play an important role in Indian economy as it contribute significantly to both agriculture and industry in terms of farm income employment and export earning . On the acreage front, India is a world leader in term of area under cotton , account for about 24 per cent of the Total world area under cotton cultivation and 5 per cent of Total cultivated area in India .In terms of production ,India ranks fourth in the world trailing behind China, Uzabikistan and USA .Maharastra is the largest cotton growing state in the country. It covers about 38 .06 lakh hectare area and is 1st in India followed by Gujarat. The total production and total productivity is 89 lakh bales and 396 kg/ha in 2016-17, respectively.

Key words: Growth,cotton Marquardt algorithm,Area,Production and Productivity

Introduction:

Cotton (*Gossypium spp.*), the 'white gold' is one of the most important cash crop in the world. Cotton is primarily a fiber crop, it is also used as a food and feed crop. Cotton seed being the world's second most oilseeds used for culinary purposes and the oil cake residue is a protein rich feed for ruminant livestock.

Cotton plays an important role in Indian economy as it contribute significantly to both agriculture and industry in terms of farm income, employment, and export earnings. The cotton textile industry is the largest industry in India which accounts for 5 per cent of the total value of production in the organized manufacturing sector and about 10 per cent of country's total export earning. About 60 million people thrive on cotton cultivation, trade and processing. India has 1569 textile mills comprising 1295 s pinning and 274 composite mills. The textile industry generates employment for about 1.2 million people in the industry itself and nearly to 21 million people in the supporting industries. Employment generation for a large number of skilled, semiskilled and unskilled persons, particularly for low-income group at the village level, is the major strength of this industry.

Historically, India has been an exporter of raw cotton to the world. As early as 1800 AD, India exported 150 thousand bales of cotton. During 19th century, cotton cultivation in India expanded rapidly and covered almost 6 million bales of cotton lint. Although domestic demand was rising, still about two-thirds of the production found export outlets. Swadeshi movement during the early year of 20th century further helped cotton cultivation and by the end of 1920 cotton covered an area of 10 million hectares producing 5.5 million bales of which two thirds was exported.

Methodology

The present chapter deals with the concise description of the data required, its collection and analytical methods used in the light of stated objectives. The specific study was concern to the analysis of growth and instability of area, production and yield of cotton in Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state. The study also aims to find out the pace of growth of area, production and yield of cotton in different period and to find out the relative contribution of area and yield toward change in production over a period of time

Results and discussion

This chapter focuses results of the present study. The results of the study were analyzed with the use of basic data collected for present investigation. The data has been processed and tabulated in the light of the objectives of this study.

Secondly, the data was analysed and,Cuddy Della Vella instability index was calculated order to detect the instability in area, production and yield of cotton crops in different sub-periods and overall period of study for Marathwada region. Another important point of study was to calculate the growth rate in area, production and yield of cotton crops in two sub-periods of study. Finally, the contributions of various components of production viz. area, yield and their interaction effect towards change in cotton production were calculated.

The whole chapter was divided into following three main sub heads and overall study period.

Average area, production and yield of cotton in Marathwada region.**Average area, production and yield of cotton crops in Marathwada region.**

The cotton was selected on the basis of maximum area coverage under these crops. There are cotton crops selected from Marathwada region. They were the average area, production and productivity of cotton crops. were calculated for two sub period viz. Period-I (1988-89 to 2001-02), period-II (2002-03 to 2015-16) and overall study period (1988-89 to 2015-16).

Average area of cotton in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra State.

The average area of cotton crop in various districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state are presented in table 1.1

It is revealed from the data in table 1.1 that, during period Ist (1988-89 to 2001-02) highest average area of cotton in Parbhani district i.e. 2730 hundred hectares (with standard deviation 541) followed by Jalna and Nanded district i.e. 1370 and 2496 hundred hectares respectively. Lowest average area of cotton was observed in Latur district it was 271 hundred hectares followed by Beed and Aurangabad district i.e. 662 and 982 hundred hectares, respectively.

Table 1.1: Average area of cotton in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state.

[Area in '00' ha]

Sr. No	Name	Period-I	Period-II	Overall
01	Aurangabad	982 (397)	3056 (986)	2019 (1288)
02	Jalna	1370 (215)	2533 (578)	1951 (730)
03	Beed	662 (334)	2261 (1031)	1462 (1109)
04	Latur	271 (55)	44 (21)	158 (123)

05	Osmanabad	NIL	120 (106)	120 (106)
06	Nanded	2496 (211)	2723 (541)	2723 (419)
07	Parbhani	2730 (541)	2238 (350)	2484 (460)
08	Hingoli	NIL	834 (150)	834 (151)
09	Marathwada	8768 (1393)	13812 (3510)	11290 (3669)
10	Maharashtra	28880 (2774)	34977 (6055)	31929 (5568)

Note: Period-I: 1988-89 to 2001-02, Period-II: 2002-03 to 2015-16, Overall Period: 1988-89 to 2015-16. Figures in bracket indicates standard deviation

Average production of cotton in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra State.

The average production of cotton crop in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state are presented in table 1.2

It is revealed from the table 1.2 that, during period 1st (1988-89 to 2001-02) highest average production of cotton in Parbhani district was 1946 hundred tonnes (with standard deviation 793) followed by Jalna and Nanded i.e. 1065 and 1456 hundred tonnes, respectively. Lowest average Production of cotton in Latur district was 188 hundred tonnes

followed by Beed and Aurangabad district i.e. 516 and 772 hundred tonnes, respectively.

During second sub-period of the study (2002-03 to 2015-16) highest average production of cotton was observed in Aurangabad district i.e. 4571 (with standard deviation 2796) hundred tonnes followed by Jalna and Parbhani districts viz. 3863 and 3287 hundred tonnes, respectively. Lowest average production of cotton was seen in Latur district i.e. 67 hundred tonnes followed by Hingoli and Osmanabad districts (1372 and 161 hundred tonnes, respectively).

Table 1.2: Average production of cotton in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

Production in '00' ha]

Sr. No	Name	Period-I	Period-II	Overall
01	Aurangabad	772 (302)	4571 (2796)	2672 (2747)
02	Jalna	1065 (393)	3863 (2211)	2464 (2111)
03	Beed	516 (290)	2427 (1492)	1472 (1434)
04	Latur	188 (57)	67 (50)	128 (81)
05	Osmanabad	NIL	161 (180)	161 (180)
06	Nanded	1456 (494)	2666 (1429)	2061 (1216)
07	Parbhani	1946 (793)	3287 (1496)	2616 (1358)
08	Hingoli	NIL	1372 (670)	1372 (670)
09	Marathwada	6123 (1976)	18417 (9064)	12270 (8979)
10	Maharashtra	22415 (6295)	50487 (19980)	36451 (20386)

Note: Period-I: 1988-89 to 2001-02, Period-II: 2002-03 to 2015-16, Overall Period: 1988-89 to 2015-16 Figures in bracket indicates standard deviation.

Average Productivity of cotton in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra State.

The average productivity of cotton in various districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state are presented in table 1.3

It is revealed from the table 1.3 that, average productivity of cotton in all districts of Marathwada region was increased from period one to period second. During period 1st (1988-89 to 2001-02) highest average

productivity of cotton was observed in Aurangabad district i.e. 141 kg per hectare (with standard deviation 44) followed by Jalna and Parbhani i.e. 130 and 120 kg per hectare, respectively. Lowest average productivity of cotton was seen in Nanded district i.e. 99 kg per hectare followed by Latur and Beed district was 115 and 130 kg per hectare, respectively.

Table 1.3: Average yield of cotton in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

[kg/ha]

Sr. No	Name	Period-I	Period-II	Overall
01	Aurangabad	141 (44)	248 (118)	194 (103)

02	Jalna	130 (34)	254 (117)	192 (105)
03	Beed	130 (26)	183 (70)	156 (58)
04	Latur	115 (36)	271 (163)	193 (140)
05	Osmanabad	NIL	201 (88)	201 (88)
06	Nanded	99 (35)	162 (88)	130 (162)
07	Parbhani	120 (42)	250 (104)	185 (102)
08	Hingoli	NIL	280 (130)	280 (130)
09	Marathwada	118 (190)	231 (512)	172 (497)
10	Maharashtra	131 (33)	242 (75)	187 (80)

Note: Period-I: 1988-89 to 2001-02, Period-II: 2002-03 to 2015-16, Overall Period: 1988-89 to 2015-16. Figures in bracket indicates standard deviation.

Conclusions

The results of the study revealed that, during overall period (1988-89 to 2015-16) maximum average area of cotton is in Nanded district was 2723 (with standard deviation 419) hundred hectares followed by Parbhani and Aurangabad district. In these districts area of cotton was 2484 and 2019 hundred hectares, respectively. Lowest average area of cotton was seen in Osmanabad district (120 hundred hectares) followed by Latur and Hingoli district, it was 158 and 834 hundred hectares, respectively. Average area under cotton crop in Marathwada region during the first period of study was 8768 kg per hectare followed by 13812 and 11290 kg per hectare during second and overall period, respectively. Average area of cotton in Maharashtra state during the first period of study was 28880 hundred hectare during sub-sequent period. It was 34977 and 31929 hundred hectare i.e. Second and overall period, respectively.

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